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“GUMAMELA”

In a farflung barrio,
Not so long ago,
A dainty gumamela bloomed,
But I guess she was doomed,
Her hues were bright as a day,
The leaves were blown to sway,
Her scent was enticing,
But some of her petals were missing,
Nonetheless of her uncanny figure,
She was a perfect view with the azure